

THE INFLUENCE OF PROCESS PARAMETERS ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BIOPOLYMER MATERIALS BASED ON CAMELINA OIL CAKE

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Abstract: *Recently, the field of biopolymer materials finds its expansion, both at the level of scientific research and on the market itself. Biopolymer materials could substitute commercial synthetic polymer materials because synthetic polymers are obtained from non-renewable sources, along being endanger the environment by their disposal. There are numerous sources for biopolymer materials synthesis. This work is a contribution to the valorization of agro-industrial waste through the synthesis of biopolymer materials. the advantage of using agro-industrial waste (e.g. straws, cakes, peels...) is the synthesis of composite materials. Used substrate was Camelina seed cake, which was obtained as a by-product of cold-pressed camelina oil production using a single screw press. The remaining cake was then milled and prepared for further analysis. Different process parameters were varied in the optimization procedure. In this paper, the influence of the process parameter pH on the mechanical properties (thickness, tensile strength, elongation at break) of the obtained materials was examined. The results showed that new biopolymer materials can be obtained at different pH values. Mechanical characteristics of the synthesized materials are in the range of mechanical characteristics of other composite materials.*

Keywords: biopolymers, camelina oil cake, pH, mechanical properties

1 INTRODUCTION

The world population increase leads to an increase in the use of different packaging materials and packaging, among which, over the years, the largest increase in market has been recorded in plastic (polymer) packaging. Due to good physical-mechanical and barrier characteristics against external environmental factors (moisture, oxygen, radiation, microorganisms, etc.), polymer packaging materials are leading in the food industry where they are used independently, as monomaterials or as multilayer and/or combined materials, in various packaging forms (Lazić and Novaković, 2010). The problem with the use of plastic packaging begins with the raw material, which is non-renewable in origin. Also, bearing in mind that the environment is affected by the entire life cycle of the packaging, the very use and eventual disposal of the used packaging contribute to a negative impact on the environment, because packaging waste accumulates.

Research into the possibility of applying more environmentally acceptable packaging materials and packaging goes in the direction of the development of natural biodegradable polymer materials. These materials doubly solve the problem of the burden on the environment caused by the use of conventional plastics - biopolymer materials come from natural, renewable raw materials and in most cases are biodegradable (Lazić and Popović, 2015). In this way, the usage of non-renewable sources and energy, whose prices are on the rise, is reduced, and non-degradable polymers are replaced by biodegradable ones, which have positive effects on the environment (Lazić and Gvozdenović, 2007).

Biopolymers have numerous advantages, and due to their biodegradability, they are increasingly finding practical use in food packaging and extending its shelf life (Basumatary et al., 2022), but also in the pharmaceutical industry and others (Udayakumar et al., 2021). Contrary to conventional polymers, biopolymer films can also be edible (Suhag et al., 2020), so they can be consumed along with the food product; can protect food from the growth of microorganisms, extending its shelf life (Hasan et al., 202); or prevent loss of moisture and impairment of the sensory characteristics of the product (De Pilli, 2020).

In recent years, the production of biodegradable packaging materials obtained from agro-industrial waste has been expanding. From an economic and ecological point of view, composite films obtained directly from secondary products of agro-industry - cake, sawdust, flour, straw, etc. are particularly interesting. The high protein, fiber, and carbohydrate content of cakes and pellets make them suitable raw materials for the production of edible biopolymer packaging materials (Popović et al., 2020), because precisely these macromolecules are more prevalent as a source for obtaining biodegradable

films and coatings. In this way, the problem of disposing and depositing waste is solved, by converting renewables into useful products, without additional energy consumption, due to the use of secondary products in their native form, without subsequent modifications.

In the Republic of Serbia, oilseeds such as sunflower, soybean, flax and pumpkin are widely represented. After the production of edible unrefined oils, a highly nutritious side product is left behind - cake, which makes up about 50% of the initial seed mass. Considering the remained quantities and the rich nutritional composition, there is a clear tendency towards the valorization of these secondary products. Potential solutions are mainly focused on the production of biofuels and animal feed, as well as the extraction of biologically valuable components (proteins, polysaccharides, phenols, etc.). However, the direction of utilization through the production of biopolymer films is also confirmed by the conducted studies, where biodegradable composite films with excellent potential for packaging food products were produced from pumpkin oil cake (Popović, 2013) and sunflower oil cake (Šuput et al., 2018).

Camelina (*Camelina sativa* (L.) Crantz) is a rediscovered protein and oilseed crop belonging to the *Brassicaceae* family, which was cultivated in the distant past (2000 BCE) in South-eastern Europe and Southwest Asia. It was grown sporadically in Europe as a conventional crop until the mid-20th century when it was replaced with more productive species like oilseed rape and sunflower (Zubr, 2010; Berti, Gesch, Eynck, Anderson & Cermak, 2016; Joudka et al., 2022). However, camelina has regained more attention in the last decade due to its numerous applications and agrotechnical and industrial benefits. Camelina may have many applications in biofuel production, cosmetology, agrochemicals, food and feed industry, etc. (Mondor & Hernández - Álvarez, 2022).

Camelina is cultivated due to its high content of protein, fat and valuable bioactive compounds, which deliver numerous beneficial effects on health. Its seed contains approximately 24-35% of crude proteins and 36% oil consisting of 40-60% polyunsaturated fatty acids, of which 35-40% is an α -linolenic fatty acid (Raczyk, Popis, Kruszewski, Ratusz & Rudzińska, 2016; Juodka et al., 2022). Unusually high levels of n-3 fatty acids and their health benefits and relative stability make camelina oil suitable for human consumption as a part of functional foods (Berhow, Vaughn, Moser, Belenli & Polat, 2014). The extraction of oil from the seed with different solvents or by mechanical pressing results in a large number of by-products (cake and meal). These by-products are regarded as valuable sources of proteins and bioactive compounds (Ilić et al., 2022).

In this paper, the possibility of valorisation of Camelina oil cake (COC) as raw material for biopolymer materials production was examined. Also, the influence of the process parameter pH on the mechanical properties (thickness, tensile strength, elongation at break) of the obtained materials was examined

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The grounded hull-less Camelina Sativa oil cake (COC) was kindly provided by Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops (Novi Sad, Serbia). All other reagents used in this study were of analytical grade.

2.2 Preparation of film solutions and film formation

Biofilms based on Camelina oil cake (COC) were prepared using the casting method. Filmogenic solution was prepared by dissolving COC (10%, w/v) in distilled water. Glycerol, as a plasticizer, was added in a concentration of 0.4 g/g oil cake. pH was adjusted to 2, 4 and 6 by addition of HCl solution and to 8, 10 and 12 by addition of NaOH solution. The resulting mixture was incubated in a water bath at 90°C for 20 min. After thermal treatment, the solution was filtered through a nylon filter, and the filtrate was used for further use. All solutions were poured (50g each) into Petri plates lined with Teflon and dried in room conditions.

2.3 Mechanical properties

Film thickness was surveyed with 1 µm sensitivity micrometer. Eight replicates were carried out on each sample.

Tensile strength (TS) and elongation at break (EB) of films were measured on the Instron Universal Testing Instrument Model No. 4301 (Instron Engineering Corp., Canton, MA) according to standard method EN ISO 527-3:2018. A rectangular film strip of 90 mm in length and 15 mm in width was used. The initial grip separation was set at 50 mm, and crosshead speed was set at 50 mm/min. The TS and EB of the strips were measured in controlled chamber, at 25°C and 75–80% relative humidity.

TS (MPa) was calculated by dividing the peak load given by the cross-sectional area of the film.

EB (%) was calculated as the percent of change by dividing film elongation at the moment of rupture by initial gage length of the specimen (50 mm) and multiplying by 100 (EN ISO 527-3:2018).

TS and EB measurements for each type of film were repeated at least five times.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To examine the effect of pH on film formation, COC film-forming solutions were prepared, varying pH in the range from 2 to 12. In the whole pH range, COC was filmogenuos, except at pH=4.0. The inability to form films at pH=4 is due to the insolubility of the protein at the specified value of pH, which represents the isoelectric point (IEP) of camellia seed protein (Ngo & Shahidi, 2021). The obtained films have very similar visual characteristics: they are dark, yellow-brown in color, non-transparent, tough and flexible. Color gradation is observed depending on the change in pH, in the sense that the films synthesized at pH values closer to the isoelectric point are lighter, and as the pH values become more extreme, the films also become darker. The different color of the films can also be a consequence of the influence of IPE, i.e. insolubility. During the preparation of films near the IEP, a smaller amount of proteins and other extractables are dissolved, and the films are probably lighter because of this. Moving away from the IEP, the extraction of filmogenic macromolecules (proteins) is greater and the color is more intense. Within each group of samples, a characteristic odor originating from the raw material is noticeable.

Films synthesized at pH 4 were not formed in the sense that they could not be dried and peeled of the non-adhesive Petri dish. The surface of the films remains moist and sticky. Therefore, the results of the characterization of these films are not presented in the paper.

3. 1 Film thickness

The obtained films had a thickness of up 193.71 ± 8.76 to 179.22 ± 3.42 , and with increasing pH value, the thickness of the films decreased.

Table 1. Film thickness (μm).

	pH2	pH6	pH8	pH10	pH12
<i>d</i> (μm)	193.71 ± 8.76	192.0 ± 7.45	183.36 ± 8.70	181.22 ± 9.27	179.22 ± 3.42

3. 2 Mechanical properties

The effects of pH on the mechanical properties of COC films are showed in Fig 1 and 2. The best mechanical properties have the films prepared at pH=12, TS is 2.12 MPa, and EB is 16.66%.

Figure 1. Tensile strength (MPa).

Figure 2. Elongation at break (%).

The results displayed that TS and EB of the COC films are influenced by the applied pH, and film with the best mechanical characteristics was prepared at pH=12. Films prepared at lower f values have a lower value of tensile strength, probably due to a smaller amount of extracted proteins, while this dependence is less pronounced regarding elongation at break.

4 CONCLUSION

COC was successfully employed to produce novel edible cast films. The impact of pH of the film solution was observed on the both TS and EB. The best properties were shown by the film prepared at pH=12, probably due to the applied extreme value of pH, with the highest extraction of filmogenic macromolecules, but also the highest IEP distance.

It is necessary to focus further research on the optimization of other process parameters (temperature, type and amount of plasticizer, etc.) in order to optimize the properties of COC films or use as a packaging material.

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